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Remediation of water from perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) with ozonation and photocatalysis: Experimental studies and numerical modeling

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ABSTRACT

The treatment of relatively high concentration (10–50 mg/L) perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) aqueous solutions is tested at ambient pH (5–7.5) in an annular photo-reactor with recirculation, and in a semi-batch bubble flow reactor with ozonation. Zinc oxide and iron-doped zinc oxide (Fe-ZnO-SL) photocatalytic nanoparticles were synthesized and immobilized on Duranit (ZnO-DN), and soda lime (Fe-ZnO-SL) beads by dip-coating and thermal annealing. In photoreactor, the recirculating rate was fixed to 30 mL/min, and a 6 W UV-C lamp emitting at 254 nm was used. Ozone was generated at concentrations $\sim 5\text{--}50\text{ g/m}^3$ from oxygen at flow rates 0.1 and 0.2 L/min. The methylene blue active substances with UV-Vis spectrophotometry (MBAS-UV-Vis) was used to measure the PFOA concentration, and evaluated with reference to Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatography-High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (UHPLC-HRMS). The advection-dispersion-reaction model, and tank-in-series model were used to estimate with inverse modeling the kinetic parameters of PFOA degradation by photocatalysis and ozonation, respectively. The experimental results obtained with the cost-effective and fast MBAS method were comparable to those of the expensive, time-consuming, and high accuracy UHPLC-HRMS method. The photocatalytic degradation of PFOA lasted a couple of days with the apparent kinetic constant depending on the catalyst type, ageing, and air injection, and the PFOA removal efficiency ranging from 22% to 93%. The PFOA removal efficiency by ozonation varied from 32% to 78%, depending on the gas flow rate, the initial PFOA concentration, and ozone concentration. Numerical modeling reveals that ozonation is dominated by the direct ozone oxidation over early times, and indirect oxidation by generated active species over late times. Short-chain congeners, such as the perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA), perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA) and perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA), were detected as intermediate products at very low concentrations, and trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) was identified as the main byproduct of ozonation. For photocatalysis, the highest PFOA removal efficiency (R_E) and lowest energy expenditure (E_m) were achieved with virgin ($R_E \sim 93\%$, $E_m \sim 0.19$ kWh/mg-PFOA) or aged ($R_E \sim 70\%$, $E_m \sim 0.11$ kWh/mg-PFOA) ZnO nanoparticles immobilized on Duranit beads. For ozonation, the highest PFOA removal efficiency was achieved at low gas flow rate and low (~ 10 mg/L) initial PFOA concentration ($R_E \sim 70\text{--}78\%$), while the energy expenditure was minimized ($E_m \sim 0.075\text{--}0.085$ kWh/mg-PFOA) for high values (~ 50 mg/L) of the PFOA concentration.

1. Introduction

There is a variety of water treatment methods to remove recalcitrant contaminants (e.g. pesticides, pharmaceuticals, personal-care products, perfluoroalkyl-substances, pathogens) from drinking water or effluents

of industrial and urban wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). The most common water treatment methods are the membrane filtration methods (e.g. microfiltration, nanofiltration, reverse and forward osmosis, ion exchange, membrane distillation), adsorption, and advanced oxidation processes (AOPs). Filtration methods produce high quality treated

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effluents, generate low solid wastes, and don't consume any chemicals, but the membranes may be clogged very quickly, and usually they operate at low flow rate and low throughput (Crini and Lichtfouse, 2019). Adsorption can be regarded as the fastest, cheapest, and most versatile technology with application to almost all types of pollutants, but it produces solid wastes which will either be landfilled or managed for regeneration (AlAqad et al., 2025; Baskar et al., 2022). On the other hand, advanced oxidation process (AOPs) such as, UV-treatment, photocatalysis, ozonation, photo-Fenton, or hybrid combinations of them are capable to mineralize recalcitrant pollutants and pathogens, without producing sludge, though chemicals might be used, and equally toxic intermediates might be formed (Saravanan et al., 2022). Moreover, during the last years, much attention has been paid on the synthesis of catalysts / photocatalysts for the degradation of recalcitrant pollutants. Three-dimensional composites generated from $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and graphene aerogels have been synthesized and used as catalyst for the photo-Fenton like activation of peroxymonosulfate (PMS) and degradation of antibiotics, such as the ciprofloxacin (Liu et al., 2025). In order to minimize the energy expenses associated with the recovery of catalytic nanoparticles from water streams, the catalyst immobilization on substrates has been adopted. One example is the in situ synthesis of CoMnN-layered double hydroxide on nickel foam and its use for the advanced oxidation of enrofloxacin (Yang et al., 2024). Oxyhydroxide-pervoskite composite catalysts have been synthesized and tested for the PMS activation and ofloxacin degradation through radical and non-radical pathways (Wang et al., 2025). The periodate (IO_4^-) based advanced oxidation of pollutants seems a cost-effective water treatment method, and the design of IO_4^- activators is a challenge (Long et al., 2021).

Due to their distinctive chemical properties and environmental stability, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) are often referred to as "forever chemicals." These substances have now been detected in relatively high levels in surface / ground water and living beings (Wanninayake, 2021). The widespread groundwater contamination with aqueous film-forming foams (AFFF) in firefighting training sites is a typical example (Liang et al., 2022). Common technologies used in water and wastewater treatment (e.g. coagulation, filtration) have been shown to be ineffective in removing PFAS (Leung et al., 2022). On the other hand, ozonation and biodegradation processes have proved insufficient to remove low levels of PFAS from potable water (Sun et al., 2018).

PFAS adsorption on anion exchange resins (ANIXm) or granular activated carbon (GAC) was successful for long-chain PFAS, while both long- and short-chain PFAS were removed satisfactorily with reverse osmosis (RO) (Appleman et al., 2014; Rahman et al., 2014). However, the energy expenditure associated with RO is notably high, and the resulting toxic solid waste needs further management (Leung et al., 2022). The performance of RO membranes depends on geometrical properties of pores, charges, and hydrophilicity and unavoidably non-equilibrium molecular dynamic simulations are needed to throw light on relevant mass transport mechanisms (Zhang et al., 2025). The predominant technologies of water treatment for the elimination of PFAS entail the adsorption process (Wanninayake, 2021). However, commonly the performance of non-selective adsorbents is hindered by the co-adsorption of other organic species while the management of the produced solid wastes is still an issue (Leung et al., 2022). To eliminate the disadvantages of filtration, such as the fouling, the combination of membrane filtration with microwave irradiation has been suggested, where PFOA was mixed with H_2O_2 and injected through a BiFeO_3 membrane, and microwave Fenton like reactions were activated (Liu et al., 2020). Moreover, significant attention has been directed towards the development of low-cost technologies capable of markedly reducing the concentration of PFAS in water: foam fractionation (Dai et al., 2019), electrochemical oxidation (Liang et al., 2022), advanced oxidation and reduction processes (Leung et al., 2022). A short review of the technologies used to remove PFAS from water sources, with emphasis placed

on AOPs is presented in Table 1.

The degradation of fluorotelomer unsaturated carboxylic acid (FTUCA) and the subsequent formation of per-fluoro-carboxylic acids (PFCAs) were found to be significantly more pronounced in ozonation process than in UV-AOP (Anumol et al., 2016). There is ambiguity regarding the effectiveness of advanced oxidation processes, despite their documented efficacy in the destruction of certain perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs), due to the potential generation of shorter-chain PFAAs (Wanninayake, 2021). In this context, the implementation of a combination of two or more remediation techniques has been demonstrated to yield superior outcomes in comparison to the application of a single technique.

The degradation mechanisms of PFAS via advanced oxidation (AOP) or reduction (ARP) processes depend on the type of reactive species and the chemical structure of the PFAS. In the photocatalytic process, the interaction of photocatalyst (e.g. titania) with UV radiation facilitates the degradation of PFAS through the oxidizing action of holes (h_{vb}^+) released in the valence band (Liu et al., 2021, 2022). The holes generate perfluoroalkyl radicals, Eq.(1a), which are unstable and decarboxylated, Eq.(1b), and the hydroxyl radicals, resulting from the breakdown of water molecules by UV-radiation, react with perfluoroalkyl radicals and create perfluoroalkyl alcohols (Gar Alalm and Boffito, 2022), Eq.(1c). The following defluorination, Eq.(1d), and hydrolysis, Eq.(1e), lead to the creation of shorter-chain PFAS, which can be further degraded in a similar way. As it has been demonstrated (Mitchell et al., 2014), hydroxyl radicals are incapable of initiating the degradation of PFOA. However, they have the capacity to engage in subsequent steps, as illustrated in Eq.(1c).

The efficiency of photodegradation processes of PFAS, such as photolysis and photocatalysis, is governed by the wavelength and power of radiation, as well as the type of dominant reactive radicals produced. However, these processes are limited by the long reaction times (Olatunde et al., 2020). Testing the composite photocatalyst WO_3/TiO_2 in photocatalytic ozonation under UVA-radiation to remove a mixture of PFAS species from water, it was found that the addition of WO_3 in TiO_2 increased the photoreaction yield, while the presence of ozone did not provide any additional advantage (Lashuk et al., 2022). Although photocatalysis is capable of remediating low levels of PFAA, the degree of defluorination is usually low, in relation to other advanced oxidation/reduction processes, due to the inefficiency of active hydroxyl radicals to break down completely the PFAA. Currently, the research efforts on photocatalysis have been concentrated on the selection of the most durable photocatalyst able to operate for a long time under solar energy, and defluorinate completely the PFAS (Leung et al., 2022).

In recent years, significant attention has also been directed towards the degradation of PFAS through the integration of photocatalysts with adsorbents, either as composite materials (Li et al., 2020) or in successive processes (Ren et al., 2023). Using the nanocomposite of zinc oxide (ZnO) & cellulose nanofiber (CNF), under solar radiation (UVA/B), aqueous solutions containing perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS), and a mixture of them at low concentration were treated successfully under continuous flow conditions (Dehghani et al., 2022). Titania immobilized on granular media exhibited rapid degradation for a wide range of PFAS (McIntyre et al., 2022). Furthermore, a wide array of oxides was tested to assess their

Table 1
Typical technologies for the removal of PFAS from water.

Method	PFAS	Degradation efficiency (%)	Remarks	Water Matrix	References
Adsorption on GAC with or without pre-ozonation	PFBS, PFHpA, PFHxS, PFOS, PFNA, PFOA	10 % / short-chain 40 %–60 % / long-chain	Pre-ozonation was effective in regenerated GAC	Effluents from wastewater treatment plants (WWTP)	(Sun et al., 2018)
GAC, AlXm, RO, AOPs, Ultrafiltration, Dissolved air flotation, River Bank Filtration	23 PFCA & PFSA	High variability ranging from less than 10 % to 99 %	RO was the most effective method; no method was able to eliminate PFAS	Drinking water and effluents from WWTP	(Appleman et al., 2014; Rahman et al., 2014)
Microwave catalytic (BiFeO ₃) membrane filtration	PFOA	66 %	Moderate catalyst coating on ceramic membrane and low hydraulic retention time facilitated the PFOA degradation via the microwave-Fenton like reaction	Synthetic water	(Liu et al., 2020)
O ₃ , O ₃ /H ₂ O ₂ UV, UV/H ₂ O ₂	FTUCA	O ₃ : GW/91 %; SW/75 % O ₃ /H ₂ O ₂ : GW/91 %; SW/57 % UV: 1 %	Production of PFCA at higher percentage for O ₃ than for UV/H ₂ O ₂	Groundwater (GW), Surface Water (SW)	(Anumol et al., 2016)
Photocatalysis, UVC, In ₂ O ₃ commercial & calcination of Indium-benzenedicarboxylate (In-BDC)	PFOA	In-BDC: 100 % Commercial: 35 %	Higher photocatalytic activity of In-BDC due to its better hydrophilicity	Synthetic water	(Liu et al., 2021)
Catalyzed H ₂ O ₂ propagation (CHP)	PFOA	89 %	Generated superoxide and hydroperoxide mineralize PFOA	Groundwater for in situ chemical oxidation	(Mitchell et al., 2014)
Photocatalytic Ozonation WO ₃ /TiO ₂ , UVA	PFOA, PFHxS, PFBS, 6:2 FTS, GenX	4–24 %	Photocatalytic ozonation ~ photocatalysis > photolysis > ozonation	Synthetic water	(Lashuk et al., 2022)
Adsorption/ Photocatalysis Fe/TiO ₂ /AC composite materials	PFOA	> 90 %	The synergistic adsorption and photocatalysis enabled the “concentrate-&-destroy” strategy	Synthetic water	(Li et al., 2020)
Adsorption/ Photocatalysis Ga/TiO ₂ /AC composite materials	PFOS	75 %	The h ⁺ holes and O ₂ [•] radicals control the PFOS degradation, first into PFOA which is then decarboxylated and defluorinated	Synthetic water	(Zhu et al., 2021)
Adsorption (Ad) Desorption (Des) & Photocatalysis (PC) UVC/sulfite	PFOA	Ad: 95–99 %; Des: 70–85 %; PC: 83–100 %	The PG-PB (pine bark grafted with amine groups) sorbent had a high PFOA adsorption capacity, was regenerated and reused; the PFOA photodegradation and defluorination efficiency was quite high.	Synthetic water	(Ren et al., 2023)
Photocatalysis UVA/B sunlight ZnO/cellulose	PFOS, PFOA	94–100 %	The PFAS mixture and the WWTP samples were more difficult to degrade as compared to single PFAS	Synthetic water and enriched effluents of WWTP	(Dehghani et al., 2022)
Photocatalysis, UVC Silica granular media with TiO ₂ Addition of nucleophiles (sodium hydroxide and sodium thiosulfate)	17 PFAS (PFAA, PFSA, PFCA)	> 88 %	Rapid PFAS degradation and significant defluorination by combining photocatalytic with nucleophilic attack	Stormwater from AFFF-impacted site	(McIntyre et al., 2022)
Bismuth oxyiodide (BiOI) fungal biocatalyst (FBC) BiOI - FBC	PFOA	35 % 40 % 90 %	The photocatalytic decomposition of PFOA avoids the generation of 5:3 FTCA carboxylic acid which inhibits the fungal biodegradation	Synthetic water	(Khan et al., 2023)
Photocatalysis, UVC Zero valent iron nanoparticles	PFNA PFOS PFOA	90 % 88 % 46 %	The PFAS degradation rates in WWTP effluent were lower than those in deionized water, while PFAS was degraded more efficiently at pH 3.0 using bare than polymer-coated nZVI	WWTP effluent	(Xia et al., 2022)
Hexagonal boron nitride (hBN), UVC / VUV	PFOS PFOA	65 % > 99 %	The electrical expenditure for PFOA and PFOS removal were 2.7 and ~50 kWh/m ³ , respectively	Groundwater from AFFF-impacted site & synthetic water	(Qanbarzadeh et al., 2023)(Tenorio et al., 2020)
UV/sulfite	15 PFAS	High variability among PFAS	Long-chain PFSA and PFCA were degraded easily but short-chain PFSA fluorotelomer sulfonic acids (FTS) were recalcitrant	Diluted groundwater from AFFF-impacted site	
Ion-exchange resin (IXR) Resin regeneration, Distillation Electrochemical oxidation (EO) of regenerant still bottom (SB)	PFAS mixture	80–98 % for PFOA and PFOS	The energy expenditure to treat groundwater by IXR-EO treatment train was 0.131–0.161 kWh/m ³ for PFOA and 0.071–0.094 kWh/m ³ for PFOS	Groundwater from AFFF-impacted site	(Liang et al., 2022)
Ion-exchange resin (IXR) Resin regeneration by methanol/ ethanol/ NaOH, Distillation Treatment of “high” (C > 100 mg/L) and “low” (C < 1 µg/L) PFAA concentrations in plasma reactors with Ar	High concentration PFAS mixture	99.9 % long-chain 99 % short-chain	> 99 % of the total oxidizable precursors (TOP) was removed from SB; the fluorine recovery was ~47–117 %; the total energy expenditure for the treatment of PFOA and PFOS from SB ranged from 380 to 830 kWh/m ³	PFAS-contaminated groundwater from firefighting training areas of former Air Force Base	(Singh et al., 2020)

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Method	PFAS	Degradation efficiency (%)	Remarks	Water Matrix	References
GAC filters and Reverse osmosis	PFOA, PFOS	89 % PFOA 86 % PFOS	Preoxidation, sedimentation, sand filtration or ozonation do not influence sensibly the removal of PFOA & PFOS	Drinking water treatment plant	(Flores et al., 2013)
Adsorption, filtration ozonation	PFOA, PFOS, PFHxA, PFHxS	80 % PFOA	Reclamation plants in Australia take treated water directly from WWTPs and treat it further to produce high quality recycled water	Effluents of WWTPs	(Thompson et al., 2011)
Photocatalytic ozonation TiO ₂ , UVC	PFOA	2 % O ₃ 17.5 % UV 27 % UV/O ₃ 45 % UV/O ₂ /TiO ₂ 99 % UV/O ₃ /TiO ₂	PFOA anion was converted to PFOA radical by direct electron transfer, the radical was decarboxylated to produce perfluoroheptyl radical, and then was oxidized to form PFHpA by hydroxyl radical which was produced from O ₃	Synthetic water	(Huang et al., 2016)
UV, ozonated air fractionation (OAF), air fractionation (AF) and combined UV/ozone	Mixture of PFCA and PFSA	17 % UV 73 % UV/O ₃ 81 % AF 95 % OAF	With fractionation technologies it was easier to remove PFSA than PFCA because PFSA is more hydrophobic than PFCA, while it was much more difficult to remove the short-chain PFAS	Water synthesized from firefighting foam	(Dai et al., 2019)

performance for the UV-photocatalytic degradation of PFAS. The use of bismuth oxyiodide in conjunction with a fungal biocatalyst has been demonstrated as an effective approach for the remediation of PFOA (Khan et al., 2023). Moreover, zero-valent iron nanoparticles (nZVI) were able to decompose perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), PFOS, and PFOA under UV radiation, at pH = 3 (Xia et al., 2022). A comparative analysis of the photodegradation capacity of Indium oxide (In₂O₃), Gallium oxide (Ga₂O₃) and TiO₂ showed that In₂O₃ was the most efficient one, but its efficiency was reduced when using real wastewater (Xu et al., 2017). Hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) was proposed for PFOA and PFOS photo-degradation (Qanbarzadeh et al., 2023).

Though photocatalytic processes are capable of decomposing long-chain PFAS (e.g., PFOA and PFOS), limited information is available for the photocatalytic degradation of short-chain PFAS (Liu et al., 2022). Short-chain PFAS are difficult to breakdown and alternative methods such as the UV/sulfite treatment (Tenorio et al., 2020), electrochemical oxidation (Liang et al., 2022), and plasma treatment (Singh et al., 2020) have been suggested. During the last years, attention has been paid on pre-concentration and destruction methods, where dilute PFAS solutions are treated in two steps. For instance, a dilute PFAS solution could first be treated with a photocatalyst/activated carbon composite to facilitate the PFAS sorption on the pore structure of material, and then photocatalytic destruction of adsorbed PFAS molecules to occur (Zhu et al., 2021). Although the photodegradation tests of PFAS proved effective when artificial water was utilized, their efficacy was found to be limited when natural water or wastewater was employed (Tian et al., 2015).

Previous studies showed that the oxidation of PFOS by ozone, ozone-UV, ozone-hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), and Fenton reactants was ineffective (Schröder and Meesters, 2005). Conversely, the post-treatment of the effluent of a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) with ozonation led to a removal efficiency 80 % for PFOS and 25 % for PFOA (Thompson et al., 2011). In another study of drinking water treatment with a variety of methods (e.g. filtration, reverse osmosis, ozonation), it was found that the overall PFOA and PFOS removal efficiency was 89 % and 86 % while the corresponding efficiency for the ozonation step was 9 % and 2 %, respectively (Flores et al., 2013). In a comparative analysis of PFOA decomposition by ozonation, UV photolysis, UV/TiO₂ photocatalysis, and photocatalytic ozonation, the PFOA removal efficiency was 0.5 % for low dosage ozonation, and 99 % for photocatalytic ozonation (Huang et al., 2016). Furthermore, when ozonation at ambient pH (4–5) for a period of a few minutes was followed by a rise of pH to 11 and continued ozonation of high dosage for a few hours, the degree of PFOA and PFOS degradation was 85–100 % (Lin et al., 2012). Depending on the imposed conditions and materials used, a large variability in the PFAS removal efficiency has been observed for photocatalysis and ozonation. Moreover, it seems that ozonation is favored for high ozone

dosage and alkaline conditions. From this perspective, it would be worthwhile to explore the extent to which the dosage of ozone influences the efficiency of PFOA removal at ambient pH values.

In the context of the "concentrate and destroy" concept, it would be worthwhile to examine the potential to destruct PFAS contained at relatively high concentrations (>1 mg/L) in a water matrix. This examination should be performed using two common and easily scalable advanced oxidation processes: (i) photocatalytic PFOA degradation in a photo-reactor equipped with immobilized photocatalyst; (ii) PFOA ozonation in a semi-batch bubble flow reactor. The overall objective of the present work is to assess the capacity of immobilized ZnO-based photocatalysts and ozonation over ambient pH values ranging from 5 to 7 to reduce the PFOA concentration in water solutions. The specific objectives of the study are: first, to reduce the PFOA concentration in water solutions from elevated levels (>10 mg/L); second, to estimate the kinetic parameters for both processes (photocatalysis, ozonation) with inverse modeling, by using true-to-the-physics numerical models; third, to compare the performance of ZnO-based photocatalysis with that of ozonation, in terms of PFOA removal efficiency and energy consumption per unit mass of degraded PFOA; fourth, to evaluate the reliability of the measurements obtained with the methylene blue active substance (MBAS) coupled with UV-Vis spectrophotometry method. The MBAS method has been proven to be a quick and simple method that does not require high-throughput equipment. It has successfully been used for single PFAS analysis with a detection limit of approximately 0.5 mg/L. However, it is important to note that MBAS has never been empirically validated in reactive systems.

ZnO and Fe-doped-ZnO photocatalytic nanoparticles were synthesized and immobilized on two non-porous substrates, Duranit beads (80 % SiO₂-20 % Al₂O₃), and soda lime beads, by dip-coating and thermal annealing. Photocatalyst-coated beads were packed into the annular space, left between the cylindrical wall of the stainless steel reactor and a co-axial UV-C lamp, irradiating at 254 nm. The treated solution recirculates continuously between the void space of photo-reactor and an external tank at a constant flow rate. Ozonation was conducted in a cylindrical and stainless steel column, where the ozone was produced from a high voltage corona discharge plasma by regulating the flow rate of oxygen at 0.1 and 0.2 L/min, with the aid of a mass gas flow controller. The PFOA concentration was measured with two methods: (1) the MBAS method and UV-Vis spectrophotometry; (2) Liquid Chromatography-High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (LC-HRMS). Two numerical models were used to interpret the results in terms of kinetic parameters estimated with inverse modeling. A one-dimensional advection-dispersion-reaction model was used to estimate the apparent 1st order kinetic constant governing the rate of the photocatalytic PFOA degradation. A modified tank-in-series model with

backflow was used to estimate the kinetic parameters of the direct and indirect PFOA degradation by ozonation. A comparison was conducted between the two approaches in terms of their effectiveness in removing PFOA, the duration of the treatment process, and the energy consumption per unit mass of PFOA degraded. In addition, guidelines were provided to enhance the application of these approaches in the degradation of PFAS.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Iron (III) nitrate nonahydrate $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck, ACS reagent, purity $\geq 98\%$); sodalime spheres of diameter 5 mm (Merck); Duranit inert balls of diameter 3–5 mm (80 % SiO_2 - 20 % Al_2O_3 , VEREINIGTE FÜLLKÖRPER-FABRIKEN-VFF); Zinc acetate dihydrate $\text{Zn}[\text{CH}_3\text{COO}]_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (ZAC, Honeywell, ACS reagent, purity $\geq 98\%$); hydrofluoric acid HF (Honeywell, analytic grade, 48 % w/w); Sulfuric acid H_2SO_4 (Honeywell, analytical grade, 96 %); sodium hydroxide NaOH (Honeywell, analytical grade, purity $\geq 98\%$); Methylene blue (Honeywell, dye content = 82 %); Chloroform (Honeywell, purity $\geq 99.8\%$); Citric acid (Honeywell, purity $\geq 99.5\%$); Sodium citrate (Honeywell, purity $\geq 99\%$); Hydrochloric acid HCl (Honeywell, 37 % w/w); PFOA (Sigma-Aldrich, purity $\geq 95\%$); tri-distilled water (3DW) was used for the preparation of photocatalysts and solutions.

2.2. Fabrication of immobilized photocatalysts

ZnO and iron-doped ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized and immobilized on two types of substrates (Duranit and soda lime beads, respectively). In the past, such photocatalysts have been tested for the degradation of methylene blue (dye), phenol, and lindane (pesticide) in water solutions, and details for their fabrication, characterization, and testing are reported elsewhere (Karavasilis et al., 2023, 2022, 2021a,b; Karavasilis and Tsakiroglou, 2021). A short description of the preparation method for each photocatalyst is given below. The immobilization of ZnO nanoparticles on the surface of Duranit beads with diameter 3–5 mm (Karavasilis et al., 2023, 2022) was carried out as follows: (1) the beads are washed with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid, chromo sulfuric acid, and deionized water; (2) the beads are immersed in 0.5 M NaOH solution for 30 min at 80 °C; (3) the beads are separated from the solution and placed in refractory trays which are filled with 0.3 M zinc acetate dihydrate solution, as precursor, until complete coverage; (4) the trays are placed into two programmable ovens for 2 h, first in a conventional oven (BINDER) at increasing temperatures 80 °C, 110 °C, 140 °C, and then in a high temperature tubular furnace (LENTON) at 430 °C; (5) the beads are rinsed with distilled water to separate the residual ZnO powder from the ZnO-coated beads. A similar procedure was followed to synthesize and deposit iron-doped ZnO nanoparticles on sodalime beads of diameter 5 mm (Karavasilis et al., 2022; Karavasilis et al., 2021a): (1) the beads are immersed into dense hydrofluoric acid for 10 min to roughen their surface and washed with tri-distilled water (3DW); (2) the beads are immersed in sodium hydroxide solution for 30 min at 80 °C; (3) the beads are separated from the solution, and placed in refractory trays filled with a mixture 0.2 M of zinc acetate dihydrate and 0.05 M iron nitrate as precursors; (4–5) the aforementioned steps of thermal treatment and washing are followed.

2.3. Experimental procedures for PFOA photodegradation

The photodegradation of PFOA was tested in a fixed bed reactor consisting of a cylindrical stainless steel tube with a hemispherical base. A UV lamp with nominal power 6 W (Phillips) emitting at wavelength 254 nm was inserted in a glass housing, which rested on a coiled spring mounted on the base of the reactor (Fig. 1). The photocatalyst-coated beads were packed in the annular space between the glass housing ($D_1 =$

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the setup for a photo-reactor with the continuous recirculation of liquid between it and an external vessel.

2.28 cm) and the internal wall of the column ($D_2 = 4.68$ cm) (Fig. 1). Due to the spherical shape of the photoreactor base, an equivalent cylindrical length, L_e , was defined by equating the internal volume of reactor with the volume of an equivalent annular space of identical diameters. A peristaltic pump (Astra Pool) recirculated the aqueous solution between the photoreactor and an external tank (Fig. 1). The entire system was placed inside a thermostatted incubator (Friocell) to keep the temperature constant at 25 °C. A set of experiments were conducted in two photoreactors of different length with constant recirculation flow rate $Q = 30$ mL/min, and variable liquid volume in the external tank. Specifically, the following experiments were conducted (Table 2): (1) PFOA photocatalysis with the ZnO-coated Duranit beads; (2) PFOA photocatalysis with the Fe-doped ZnO-coated soda lime beads; (3,4) photolysis of high and low PFOA concentration in an empty photoreactor with the UV-light on; (5) PFOA sorption on the Fe-doped ZnO-coated soda lime beads in dark; (6) PFOA photocatalysis with the Fe-doped ZnO-coated soda lime beads after their use for a period of 175 h (aging); (7) PFOA photocatalysis with the used Fe-doped ZnO-coated soda lime beads after their use for a period of 350 h, and under the continuous injection of humidified air in the recirculation tank; (8) PFOA photocatalysis with the ZnO-coated Duranit beads after their use for a period of 100 h (aging). From time to time, 4 mL of liquid sample were collected from the recirculation tank for the analysis of PFOA concentration. At the end of each experiment liquid sample of 20 mL was kept to detect the fluoride concentration.

2.4. Experimental setup for PFOA ozonation

All experiments were conducted in semi-batch mode in a stainless steel cylindrical column of 3.6 cm inner diameter and 50 cm height. A fixed volume of 250 mL of the aquatic solution was placed in the column. With the aid of a mass gas flow controller (SmartTrack 50, SI-ERRA), pure oxygen was injected in an ozone generator (LAB2B, Suez) at constant flow rate 0.1 or 0.2 L/min. For the removal of the moisture and dust from the oxygen, a high efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filter and a silica gel column were inserted before the high voltage generator which is a corona plasma reactor converting oxygen to ozone (Fig. 2). The ozone rich gas was bubbled through a porous cylindrical diffuser, adapted at the bottom of the column. The ozone concentration in injected gas was monitored on-line with a PC-controlled ozone analyzer (BMT965 MesstechnikGmbH). A number of sensors were inserted across the metallic column to detect continuously the pH (Smartpat pH 2390), temperature (Autosen, AT011-AT014), and redox potential (Smartpat

Table 2
Experimental conditions of photo-degradation tests.

Experiment	Catalyst	Light source	Equivalent length L_e (cm)	Liquid volume in reactor, V_R (mL)	Liquid volume in tank, V_T (mL)	Initial PFOA concentration C_0 (mg/L)	Initial PFOA mass M_0 (mg)
ZnO-DN	Duranit beads coated with ZnO	UV-C, 254 nm	38	200	50	27.1	6.775
Fe-ZnO-SL	Sodalime beads coated with fresh Fe-doped ZnO	UV-C, 254 nm	38	200	50	42.1	10.525
PHL-1	No packing material	UV-C, 254 nm	32.5	425	125	57.6	31.68
PHL-2	No packing material	UV-C, 254 nm	32.5	425	125	14.1	7.755
Fe-ZnO-SL-NoUV	Sodalime beads coated with used (75 h) Fe-doped ZnO	No light	38	200	100	42.1	12.63
Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag	Sodalime beads coated with used (175 h) Fe-doped ZnO	UV-C, 254 nm	38	200	250	44.07	19.831
Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag-Air	Sodalime beads coated with used (350 h) Fe-doped ZnO & injection of humidified air	UV-C, 254 nm	38	200	250	47.39	21.325
ZnO-DN-Ag	Duranit beads coated with used (100 h) ZnO	UV-C, 254 nm	38	200	250	47.21	21.24
ZnO-DN-Ag2	Duranit beads coated with used (250 h) ZnO	UV-C, 254 nm	38	175	250	8.4	3.57

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the experimental setup for ozonation tests.

ORP 1590). A peristaltic pump was used to recirculate the liquid between the column reactor and the holder of dissolved ozone sensor (CS6530/T6058, Chunye, CN). The signals from all sensors (4–20 mA) were transmitted and stored in the PC via data-acquisition cards (ADAM 4561 & ADAM 4117, Advantech). At high concentrations, PFOA behaves as surfactant so that very frequently foam was generated in the upper part of the column, overflowing with the exhaust gas from the outlet port. For this reason, the outflowing fluids were driven to a column of Plexiglas to separate the liquid from gas phase (foam trap), while a second peristaltic pump returned the collected liquid back to the column reactor (Fig. 2). In this manner, potential losses of liquid phase were avoided. The entire system was placed under a fume hood for safety reasons (Fig. 2). Every 1 h, a liquid sample of 4 mL was collected from a lateral sampling port, located at the lower part of the column. At the end of each experiment liquid sample of 20 mL was collected to detect the fluoride concentration.

2.5. Analytical methods

The PFOA concentration in liquid samples collected from the reactors, was measured with by the methylene blue active substance (MBAS) extraction method in combination with the UV-Vis spectroscopy, a method that has widely been used over the high concentration range of long-chain perfluoro carboxylic acids (Brusseau et al., 2019; Moody and Field, 2000). The PFOA of aquatic solutions were extracted along with methylene blue (MB) into chloroform to form 1:1 ion-pairs so that the MB-PFOA concentration was determined spectrophotometrically. The method provided linear calibration plot over the range 10^{-7} – 10^{-5} M.

Each liquid sample collected during the experiments was transferred to a mixing funnel, where 2 mL of citrate buffer 0.01 M (to prevent extraction of unionized acid) and 2 mL of Methylene Blue solution 0.001 M were added. Each aqueous solution was extracted with 20 mL of chloroform in a tightly capped centrifuge tube. The tubes were shaken moderately to minimize the emulsification, and then were allowed to

stand for 10–15 min. This procedure was repeated three times. Afterwards, the tubes were centrifuged to break any foam and/or emulsion. The aqueous layer was aspirated and the absorbance of the MB layer in organic phase was measured at the wavelength 652 nm in a 1 cm quartz cell in an UV-1900 UV-VIS Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu).

Moreover, liquid samples collected from one photocatalysis and three ozonation tests were analyzed for PFAS target analysis by means of Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatography – High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (UHPLC-HRMS) using Dionex UltiMate 3000 UHPLC system coupled with Orbitrap Exploris 120 MS (ThermoScientific, Waltham, USA), and the results were utilized to (1) assess the reliability of MBAS method when applied to reacting PFAS systems, and (2) detect the concentration of potential short-chain PFAS produced during advanced oxidation processes

An in-house validated method, adopted from the EPA method 533, was utilized for targeted PFAS analysis using UHPLC-HRMS. The method involves isotope dilution with isotopically labeled analogues and online solid phase extraction employing a weak anion exchange Strata X-AW cartridge. To reduce background contamination, PFAS-certified polypropylene autosampler vials were used, as well as a Restek PFAS delay column (5 μm , 50 \times 2.1 mm) to trap any PFAS from the mobile phases. The chromatographic separation column was Luna Omega PS C18 (100 \times 2.1 mm, 1.6 μm). HRMS data was acquired employing a Full Scan – targeted MS/MS (FS-tMS²) method in negative polarity electrospray ionization mode (ESI-). The PFOA [M-H]⁻ precursor ion with m/z 412.9664 (quantifier ion) and two MS/MS fragment ions with m/z 368.9768 and 168.9896 (qualifier ions) were monitored. PFOA quantification was based on an eight-point calibration curve ranging from 2.0 to 1000 ng/L with a very good linearity ($R^2=0.9993$). Quality control samples and blanks were injected along with samples to monitor contamination and carryover. Additional data on the targeted method are provided in Tables S1 and S2 in Supporting Information.

For PFAS Non-Target Analysis, the three ozonation samples, one quality control sample (QC) prepared by pooling the three samples, and a procedural blank were analyzed adopting a non-targeted screening method using UHPLC-HRMS. A Full MS Data Dependent Analysis (FS-ddMS²) was performed in the m/z range 40–600 at 120,000 mass resolution (200 m/z) for Full Scan and 30,000 resolution for MS/MS applying collision energies of 10, 25, and 50 V. The obtained HRMS data were processed using Compound Discoverer 3.3.2 Software (ThermoScientific, Waltham, USA) employing a non-targeted workflow tailored for the identification of PFAS, as described elsewhere (Jacob et al., 2021)(Jacob et al., 2021). Identification of non-target compounds was based on formula prediction from the high-resolution accurate mass (HRAM) and MS/MS spectra best fit between experimental and mzCloudTM spectral library. Accurate mass was also leveraged via searches against “Mass List” databases such as the EPA’s DSSTOX database (Grulke et al., 2019). The complete list of databases included in the processing workflow, along with an overview of the processing tree (Figure S1), is provided in the Supporting Information.

Regarding the free fluoride analysis, upon completion of each experiment, the total fluoride ion concentration was measured by means of a fluoride meter (Extech FL700 Waterproof ExStik). Preparation of the unknown solution for the measurement was done by adding a TISAB reagent to a 20 mL liquid sample. After calibration with a fluoride solution in the range of 0.1 – 10 ppm, the fluoride meter was placed inside the aqueous solution and after 25 s, the fluoride ion concentration was manually recorded.

The specific energy consumption (or energy expenditure), E_m , is defined as the energy consumed per unit mass of PFOA removed (kWh/mg). The average electrical power consumption was measured separately for each device (pumps, ozone generator, UV-lamp) during the experiments, with the aid of an Energy Meter JGQ01S-01 16 A/3680 W (EcoSavers).

2.6. Process simulation and inverse modeling

2.6.1. Modeling the PFOA photocatalytic degradation

The mass balance of the dissolved PFOA concentration along the photo-reactor, $C_P(t, z)$, is described by the advection-dispersion-reaction equation:

$$\frac{\partial C_P}{\partial t} = D_L \frac{\partial^2 C_P}{\partial x^2} - u_0 \frac{\partial C_P}{\partial x} - r_P \quad (2)$$

where t is the time, z is the axial distance from the inlet port, D_L is the longitudinal hydrodynamic dispersion coefficient, $u_0 = Q/(\varphi A)$ is the average pore velocity, φ is the bed porosity, Q is the volumetric flow rate, A is the cross-sectional area of the bed, r_P is the overall PFOA degradation rate (Fig. 1). The recirculation tank (Fig. 1) resembles a continuously stirred tank, and the mass balance for PFOA is written:

$$\frac{dC_T}{dt} = \frac{Q}{V_T} [C_P(t, z = L) - C_T] \quad (3)$$

where $C_T(t)$ and V_T are the PFOA concentration, and liquid volume in the tank, respectively. The overall rate of PFOA degradation is approximated by a pseudo-first order kinetics of the form:

$$r_P = k_r C_P \quad (4)$$

where k_r is the apparent 1st order kinetic constant (s^{-1}). The hydrodynamic dispersion coefficient is given by the following equation (Karavasilis and Tsakiroglou, 2021):

$$D_L = \frac{D_{mp}}{F\varphi} + a_L u_0 \quad (5)$$

where D_{mp} is the molecular diffusion coefficient of pollutant, a_L is the longitudinal dispersion length, and F is the electrical formation factor. In the case of unpacked reactor (photolysis), the annular geometry can be approximated as two parallel plates at distance $b = \frac{D_2 - D_1}{2}$, and the Taylor type hydrodynamic dispersion coefficient is given by (James and Chrysikopoulos, 2003):

$$D_L = D_{mp} + \frac{u_0^2 b^2}{210 D_{mp}} \quad (6)$$

If C_{P0} is the initial PFOA concentration, then, the foregoing equations are subjected to the initial conditions:

$$C_P(t = 0, x) = C_{P0} \quad (7a)$$

$$C_T(t = 0) = C_{P0} \quad (7b)$$

and boundary conditions:

$$C_P(t, x = 0) = C_T(t) \quad (8a)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_P}{\partial x}(t, x = L_e) = 0 \quad (8b)$$

With the aid of software package Athena Visual Studio 14 and Bayesian estimation (Stewart and Caracotsios, 2008), inverse modeling was carried out to match the measured PFOA concentration in recirculation tank, and estimate the apparent kinetic constant k_r .

2.6.2. Modeling the PFOA ozonation

The tanks-in-series model (TSM), used in the past to simulate the ozonation of dyes (Tokumura et al., 2009), and more recently the ozonation of oil-drilling cuttings (Kalari et al., 2023) in bubble flow reactors (Fig. 3a,b) was modified appropriately to simulate the PFOA degradation by ozone. The aqueous phase is represented by a number of n_L well-stirred tanks where the up-flow rate is equal to the backflow rate Q_L , while the gas phase is represented by a number of n_G separate tanks of constant flow rate, Q_G (Fig. 3c). The ozone dissolves in the liquid

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic diagram of a bubble flow reactor. (b) Magnification of gas bubbles moving through the liquid phase. (c) Tanks-in-series model for a semi-batch column ($n_G = 2n_L$).

phase and a fraction of dissolved ozone might be decomposed to active radicals (Sotelo et al., 1987). More specifically, ozone may be decomposed into reactive radicals, like hydroxyl (OH^\bullet), superoxide ($O_2^{\bullet-}$), ozonide ($O_3^{\bullet-}$) and hydroperoxyl (HO_2^\bullet), which might be generated in accordance with the following reactions (Gardoni et al., 2012; Zhao et al., 2004).

When produced, the aforementioned radicals may attack all organic compounds at rates higher than those of the direct reaction with ozone. The dissolved ozone and the intermediates of its decomposition contribute to the gradual direct and indirect degradation of PFOA, respectively. For the sake of simplicity, all short- or long-lived species produced from O₃ decomposition are regarded as a pseudo-component of concentration C_R able to oxidize indirectly the PFOA.

Interfacial momentum- and mass-transfer occurs between the aqueous solution of volume V_L and the gas bubbles up-flowing at rate Q_G (Fig. 3c). The liquid and gas phase are regarded as series of well-mixed

tanks with the liquid backflow rate, Q_L , being governed by the gas injection rate, geometrical characteristics of the column, and physical properties of fluids (Fig. 3c). More details on the modelling of flow hydrodynamics is reported elsewhere (ULBRECHT et al., 1985). The TSM model, as applied to PFAS ozonation, is described in detail below. Based on the PC-recorded data of sensors during the experiments, time-averaged values are calculated for the inlet ozone concentration, solution pH and temperature, to be used as input data in the TSM model. The nomenclature of symbols is given in Supporting Information (Section 5).

For each tank (Fig. 3c), mass balances are formulated for: (i) the ozone in gas and liquid phase; (ii) PFOA in liquid phase; (iii) intermediate radicals generated from ozone decomposition in liquid phase. The mass balance for ozone concentration around the j tank ($1 < j \leq n_G$) of gas phase is written (Tokumura et al., 2009)

$$\frac{dC_{O_3,j}^g}{dt} = \left(\frac{1 - \varphi_G}{\varphi_G} \right) \left(\frac{I_p}{V_L} \right) Q_G (C_{O_3,j-1}^g - C_{O_3,j}^g) - \left(\frac{1 - \varphi_G}{\varphi_G} \right) K_L a (1 + \varepsilon_{f,k}) (H_e C_{O_3,j}^g - C_{O_3,k}^l) \quad (10)$$

where

$$I_p = (n_G/n_L) = 2, \quad k = (j/I_p)$$

where the overall coefficient of ozone mass-transfer from the gas to the liquid phase, $K_L a$, is calculated as function of all pertinent dimensionless parameters, and details are given in Supporting Information (Section 3). The Henry law constant, H_e , is governed by the temperature, T , and ionic strength of solution, S_I , according to the relationship (Kalari et al., 2023)

$$H_e = \frac{R_g T}{e^{-\frac{2297}{T} + 2.659S_I - 688\frac{S_I}{T} + 12.19}} \quad (11)$$

The O₃ mass balance in the bottom tank ($j = 1$) of the gas phase yields:

$$\frac{dC_{O_3,1}^g}{dt} = \left(\frac{1-\varphi_G}{\varphi_G}\right) \left(\frac{I_P}{V_L}\right) Q_G (C_{O_3,m}^g - C_{O_3,1}^g) - \left(\frac{1-\varphi_G}{\varphi_G}\right) K_L a (1 + \varepsilon_{f,1}) (H_e C_{O_3,1}^g - C_{O_3,1}^l) \quad (12)$$

The O₃ mass balance in the headspace of the column becomes:

$$\frac{dC_{O_3,out}^g}{dt} = \left(\frac{Q_G}{V_H}\right) (C_{O_3,n_G}^g - C_{O_3,out}^g) \quad (13)$$

At each liquid tank, the Henry law is used to calculate the concentration of dissolved ozone, averaged over all liquid/gas interfaces between it and parallel gas tanks:

$$C_{O_3,i}^{l,*} = \frac{1}{I_P} \sum_{m=(i-1)I_P+1}^{I_P} H_e C_{O_3,m}^g \quad (14)$$

The mass balance for dissolved ozone around the i tank ($1 < i \leq n_L$) of liquid results in (Tokumura et al., 2009):

$$\frac{dC_{O_3,i}^l}{dt} = K_L a_L (C_{O_3,i}^{l,*} - C_{O_3,i}^l) + r_{O_3,i} + \alpha_D r_{PD,i} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{O_3,i-1}^l - C_{O_3,i}^l) + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{O_3,i+1}^l - C_{O_3,i}^l) \quad (15)$$

where α_D represents the ozone consumed per PFOA direct degradation rate. The kinetics of dissolved ozone decomposition depends on the temperature and pH according to the relationship (Sotelo et al., 1987):

$$r_{O_3,i} = -fk_{O_3,1} e^{-4964/T} C_{O_3,i}^l - fk_{O_3,2} e^{-10130/T} C_{O_3,i}^l{}^{3/2} [OH^-]_i^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

where the fraction f specifies the ratio of actual decomposition rate to the theoretical one. The ozone decomposition (Gardoni et al., 2012; Zhao et al., 2004) generates free radicals, like hydroxyl (OH^\bullet), superoxide ($O_2^{\bullet-}$), ozonide ($O_3^{\bullet-}$) and hydroperoxyl (HO_2^\bullet), which are very reactive and may trigger the indirect oxidation of PFOA. The direct oxidation of PFOA by ozone might be described by the 2nd order kinetic model (Tokumura et al., 2009):

$$r_{PD,i} = -k_{PD} C_{O_3,i}^l (C_{P,i} - C_{P,eq})^2 \quad (17)$$

where $C_{P,eq}$ is the steady-state PFOA concentration in liquid phase. The dissolved O₃ concentration in the bottom tank ($i = 1$) is given by:

$$\frac{dC_{O_3,1}^l}{dt} = K_L a (C_{O_3,1}^{l,*} - C_{O_3,1}^l) + r_{O_3,1} + \alpha r_{PD,1} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{O_3,2}^l - C_{O_3,1}^l) \quad (18)$$

Likewise, for the top tank ($i = n_L$) the mass balance takes the form:

$$\frac{dC_{O_3,n_L}^l}{dt} = K_L a (C_{O_3,n_L}^{l,*} - C_{O_3,n_L}^l) + r_{O_3,n_L} + \alpha_D r_{PD,n_L} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{O_3,n_L-1}^l - C_{O_3,n_L}^l) \quad (19)$$

If all intermediate radicals of ozone decay are regarded as one pseudo-component of concentration, C_R , then the indirect PFOA oxidation could be considered as a reaction occurring in parallel to the direct oxidation, according to the kinetic model:

$$r_{PI,i} = -k_{PI} C_{R,i} (C_{P,i} - C_{P,eq})^2 \quad (20)$$

The mass balances for the pseudo-component of intermediate radicals in the i^{th} tank ($1 < i < n_L$), bottom tank ($i = 1$), and top tank ($i = n_L$) yield:

$$\frac{dC_{R,i}}{dt} = -r_{O_3,i} + \alpha_I r_{PI,i} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{R,i-1} - C_{R,i}) + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{R,i+1} - C_{R,i}) \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{dC_{R,1}}{dt} = -r_{O_3,1} + \alpha_I r_{PI,1} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{R,2} - C_{R,1}) \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{dC_{R,n_L}}{dt} = -r_{O_3,n_L} + \alpha_I r_{PI,n_L} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{R,n_L-1} - C_{R,n_L}) \quad (23)$$

respectively. In addition, the transient change of PFOA concentration in i^{th} tank ($1 < i < n_L$), bottom tank ($i = 1$) and top tank ($i = n_L$) of liquid phase are given by:

$$\frac{dC_{P,i}}{dt} = r_{PD,i} + r_{PI,i} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{P,i-1} - C_{P,i}) + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{P,i+1} - C_{P,i}) \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{dC_{P,1}}{dt} = r_{PD,1} + r_{ID,1} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{P,2} - C_{P,1}) \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{dC_{P,n_L}}{dt} = r_{PD,n_L} + r_{ID,n_L} + \frac{Q_L}{(V_L/n_L)} (C_{P,n_L-1} - C_{P,n_L}) \quad (26)$$

respectively.

The unknown parameters of the model to estimate are: (i) the steady-state PFOA concentration, $C_{P,eq}$ which sets a lower limit that can be achieved; (ii) the ratio of actual decomposition rate to the theoretical one, f ; (iii) the direct PFOA degradation rate constant, k_{PD} ; (iv) the indirect PFOA degradation rate constant, k_{PI} ; (v) the ozone mass consumed per PFOA direct degradation rate, α_D ; (vi) the pseudo-component (O₃ decomposition products) mass consumed per PFOA indirect degradation rate, α_I . The ratio of degradation rate attributed to direct oxidation by O₃ to the total degradation rate (including direct and indirect oxidation rates), $r_{PD}/(r_{PD} + r_{PI})$, can be post-calculated.

The software package Athena Visual Studio 14 was used to simulate the ozonation process, and with the aid of its Bayesian estimator (Stewart and Caracotsios, 2008), inverse modeling and parameter estimation was carried out to match simultaneously the PFOA and dissolved O₃ concentrations at all sampling times. At every moment, space-averaged values were calculated for the concentration of PFOA, C_P , dissolved ozone, $C_{O_3}^l$, and ozone decomposition products, C_R .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. PFOA photocatalytic degradation

3.1.1. Photocatalyst morphology

Beads of the two substrates without and with the immobilized photocatalysts covering their surface are shown in Fig. 4a,b. Scanning-electron microscope (SEM) images were taken with a Zeiss Supra 35VP instrument. The morphology of the surface of ZnO-coated bead is shown in Fig. 4c, where nanoparticles of average diameter ~ 135 nm \pm 30 nm are visible. When doping the ZnO with iron, a dense "forest" of nanotubes is created with very small nanoparticles (~ 5 –10 nm) covering their surface (Fig. 4d). During the use of photocatalysts, shear stresses may cause detachment of nanoparticles from the upper layers, leading to reduction of the density of nanoparticles on the beads (Fig. 4e, f). More details on the characterization of the catalysts immobilized on the two substrates are reported elsewhere (Karavasilis et al., 2022, 2021a,b).

3.1.2. Kinetic studies of PFOA photodegradation

The software package Athena Visual Studio 14 (Stewart and Caracotsios, 2008) was used to estimate the apparent kinetic constant of photocatalysis for the various types of photo-degradation tests and photocatalysts (Table 3), by matching the numerical solution of Eqs.(2),

Fig. 4. (a) Duranit beads before and after their coating with ZnO nanoparticles; (b) Sodalime beads before and after their coating with Fe-doped ZnO nanoparticles. Scanning-electron microscopy (SEM) images of (c) fresh ZnO nanoparticles immobilized on Duranit beads, (d) fresh Fe-doped ZnO nanoparticles immobilized on sodalime beads, (e) used ZnO nanoparticles immobilized on Duranit beads, (f) used Fe-doped ZnO nanoparticles immobilized on sodalime beads.

Table 3

Kinetic constant for the pseudo-first order photocatalytic PFOA degradation and final fluoride concentration.

Exper.	ZnO-DN	Fe-ZnO-SL	PHL-1	PHL-2	Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag	Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag-Air	ZnO-DN-Ag	ZnO-DN-Ag2
C_{P0} (mg/L)	27.1	42.1	57.6	14.1	44.07	47.39	47.21	8.4
C_{PT} (mg/L)	2.0	16.4	43.24	8.97	34.46	30.19	13.93	1.95
$(C_{P0}-C_{PT})/C_{P0}$	0.926	0.610	0.249	0.364	0.218	0.363	0.705	0.768
$k_r \times 10^6$ (s ⁻¹)	6.335 ± 1.139	2.393 ± 0.614	1.226 ± 0.298	2.794 ± 1.683	0.495 ± 0.101	1.248 ± 0.309	2.26 ± 0.184	1.46 ± 0.218
R^2	0.0299	0.0251	0.0116	0.0184	0.0107	0.0102	0.0051	0.1571
Final F ⁻ concent. (mg/L)	0.9	0.6	7.2	2.4			3.3	
δ_f (%)	5.2	3.4	72.5	67.7			14.4	

(3), to the PFOA concentration measured in recirculation tank as a function of time (Fig. 5a). The Bayesian estimator of the software, except of the parameter value, provides the 95 % highest posterior density (\pm HPD) interval, which is a measure of the uncertainty embedded in the parameter values. Each HPD value contains 95 % of the mass of the posterior distribution around the centre of the distribution, and all values inside the interval are more likely to represent the parameter than the values outside the interval. The lower the HPD interval, and the lower the sum of squares of residuals (R^2), the higher the success of model adaptability to the experimental data (Table 3). Simulated results of the transient responses of PFOA removal efficiency, defined by the ratio $(C_{P0} - C_P)/C_{P0}$, are compared with experimental measurements in Fig. 5a for all photoreaction systems tested. It seems that the model fits satisfactorily all datasets (Fig. 5a,b, Table 3). Without activating the UV-light, no sensible change of PFOA concentration was observed (Fig. 5a), which means that the PFOA sorption onto Fe-doped ZnO photocatalyst is negligible in relation to the PFOA concentrations detected. With reference to the apparent kinetic constant (Table 3), it is

evident that the decomposition of PFOA occurs faster on ZnO-DN than on Fe-ZnO-SL catalyst (Fig. 5a, Table 3). Such differences in photocatalytic activity could be attributed to the chemistry and microscopic structure (Fig. 4c,d) of photocatalytic nanoparticles, nanocomposite heterostructures, catalytic dosage, pH and temperature (Singh et al., 2022, 2024). Though a higher PFOA degradation rate would be anticipated for Fe-ZnO heterostructure, the two catalysts have been deposited on different substrates (Fig. 4a,b), and probably the surface of ZnO nanoparticles might be better exposed to UV-radiation than the needle-like Fe-ZnO nanotubes (Fig. 4c,d). Simple PFOA photolysis (PHL-1, PHL-2) is equally efficient or even faster than photocatalytic PFOA degradation on Fe-ZnO-SL (Fig. 5a, Table 3). After their extensive use (aging), the efficiency of both photocatalysts Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag and ZnO-DN-Ag was reduced (Fig. 5a, Table 3) due to the catalyst mass losses from the substrate (Fig. 4e,f). It's worth mentioning that ZnO nanoparticles are characterized by excellent recyclability, and for this reason, they are used widely as photocatalytic materials for the treatment of contaminated wastewater (Sharma et al., 2025). On the other hand, the

Fig. 5. (a) Measured (symbols) vs simulated (solid lines) transient responses of PFOA removal efficiency in recirculation tank (Table 2). (b) Comparison of the transient responses of PFOA removal efficiency for the same photocatalyst by using the MBAS and UHPLC-HRMS methods of analysis (symbols: measured data; solid lines: simulated data). (c) Energy consumption per unit mass of PFOA degraded during photocatalytic tests, calculated from experimental data.

performance of Fe-ZnO-SL photocatalyst was enhanced profoundly with the continuous injection of humidified air in the recirculation tank, leading to the increase of the concentration of oxidative species in the reactor (Fig. 5a, Table 3). Due to the broad diversity of photocatalysts used, the reduction of the photocatalytic performance by ageing, and the long reaction times, the repetition of experiments was limited. However, for assessing the MBAS method reliability, one of the catalysts (ZnO-DN), after its extended use for 250 h, was reused in another test (ZnO-DN-Ag2) that lasted for 20 days, and where the PFOA concentration was measured with the UHPLC-HRMS method (Fig. 5b), while the initial and final PFOA concentrations were measured by both methods. Evidently, the longest period of photocatalyst reuse leads to slower PFOA degradation rate (Table 3, Fig. 5b). Nevertheless, the two responses obtained by the two methods of analysis are comparable over early times (Fig. 5b) confirming the repeatability of photo-degradation process, and reliability of MBAS method for reactive systems. In addition, the initial, 8.56 mg/L, and final, 2.06 mg/L, PFOA concentrations, measured with the MBAS method, were comparable to the corresponding ones, 8.4 mg/L (deviation=1.8 %) and 1.9 mg/L (deviation=7.8 %), measured with the UHPLC-HRMS (Fig. 5b).

For the calculation of the specific energy consumption (or energy expenditure), E_m , as a function of time (Fig. 5c), the measured PFOA mass degraded was taken in account. It seems that asymptotically, the energy expenditure of the two photocatalysts, ZnO-DN and Fe-ZnO-SL is comparable each to other, while the energy expenditure of ZnO-DN-Ag is much less than that of Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag, and comparable to that of Fe-ZnO-Ag-Air (Fig. 5c). It's worth mentioning that the limited PFOA degradation during the first hours leads to a sharp increase of energy expenditure, but gradually, as the PFOA degradation proceeds, the energy expenditure tends to decrease, and stabilizes at late times (Fig. 5c).

In terms of PFOA removal efficiency (Fig. 5a) and energy expenditure (Fig. 5c), the ZnO-DN and ZnO-DN-Ag photocatalysts displayed the best performance. The energy expenditure is scale-dependent, is governed by the volume of treated liquid and initial pollutant mass, and is anticipated to decrease respectively with both parameters increasing (Hiwarkar et al., 2021). Indeed, the minimum energy expenditure occurred for ZnO-DN-Ag, Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag-Air and PHL-1 where the treated volume (450–550 mL) and initial PFOA mass (21–32 mg) were quite high (Table 2).

The measured values of fluoride concentration, measured at the end of photodegradation, could implicitly be correlated with the degree of defluorination, d_f , of PFOA which quantifies the percentage of fluorine contained in the degraded mass of PFOA, that has been converted into free fluoride anions, and is defined by

$$d_f = \frac{C_F MW_{PFOA}}{n_F (C_{P0} - C_{PT}) MW_F} \quad (27)$$

where C_{PT} , C_F are the measured final PFOA and F^- concentrations, MW_{PFOA} , MW_F are the PFOA and F^- molecular weights, and n_F is the total number of fluorine atoms per molecule of PFOA ($n_F=15$). It is evident that the degree of defluorination is quite high for photolysis, and limited for photocatalysis (Table 3). However, a significant degree of uncertainty is embedded in the fluoride concentrations, detected by the sensor at the end of photocatalysis tests (Table 3), as the measurements of fluoride detector are affected positively or negatively by the coexistence of other ions in solution, and therefore more reliable techniques are required (e.g. ion chromatography) to measure precisely this parameter.

3.2. PFOA ozonation

To assess the repeatability of ozonation experiments under comparable conditions, a series of tests were repeated three times for PFOA initial concentration close to ~ 50 mg/L, gas flow rate 0.1 L/min, and three values of injected ozone concentration ($\sim 5, 10, 20$ g/Nm³). It seems that the uncertainty of the PFOA removal efficiency (Fig. 6b-d) is proportional to the uncertainty embedded into the measured values of dissolved ozone concentration (Fig. 6a), which widens with the injected ozone concentration increasing. The ozone dissolution from the up-flowing gas bubbles to aqueous phase (Fig. 3a) is affected not only by well-controlled parameters such as the gas flow rate, the liquid volume, the reactor dimensions, the injected O₃ concentration, but also by unforeseeable and not-well controlled factors such as the size and density of generated bubbles, the flow regime within the reactor, the dispersive mixing of gas with water throughout the column, the fluctuations of ozone concentration in injected gas, and the rate of dissolved ozone decomposition. As the ozone concentration in gas phase increases, the dissolved O₃ concentration also increases but becomes more sensitive to the aforementioned factors leading to higher uncertainties for the concentration of dissolved ozone and radicals, and the subsequent rates of direct and indirect oxidation of PFOA (Fig. 6b-d).

Simulated results of the transient responses of PFOA removal efficiency, and dissolved O₃ concentrations are compared with experimental measurements in Figs. 7, 8, 9 for tests conducted at flow rate 0.1, 0.2, 0.1 L/min, and initial PFOA concentration $C_{P0} = 50.0, 10.0, 10.0$ mg/L, respectively. The simulations were performed at the optimal parameter values, estimated by matching the numerical predictions of the tanks-in-series model ($n_L = 2$) to the measured transient responses of PFOA and dissolved ozone concentrations.

Fig. 6. Repeatability of ozonation tests for PFOA initial concentration ~ 50 mg/L. Transient responses of (a) dissolved ozone concentration, and (b-d) PFOA removal efficiency as the ozone concentration in injected gas varies: (b) 5–6 g/m³, (c) 10–11 g/m³, (d) 20–22 g/m³.

For low flow rate and high initial PFOA concentration, the dissolved O₃ concentration is predicted satisfactorily (Fig. 7b,d,f,h), accounting for that: (a) any fluctuations of O₃ in injected gas are ignored in simulations; (b) the reduction of the surface tension in gas/liquid interfaces, due to the high PFOA concentration, lead to foam occupying the upper part of reactor and resulting in the outflow of gas/water mixture, the separation of gas from liquid and the recirculation of liquid phase to the reactor (Fig. 2). Within the timeframe of 6 h, the percentage of degraded PFOA did not exceed 50 % (Fig. 7a,c,e), and reached 57 % only when the ozone concentration became quite high (Fig. 7 g). At early times, the PFOA degradation is governed by the direct oxidation, while at late times, the indirect oxidation via ozone decomposition products prevails (Fig. 7a,c,e,g). The concentration of ozone decomposition products in aqueous phase, C_R , is very low at early times, and becomes discernible at late times, especially when the ozone concentration in gas phase becomes quite high (Fig. S2a-d), so that gradually the direct oxidation diminishes, the rate of PFOA degradation decreases, and the indirect oxidation prevails (Fig. 7a,c,e,g).

At high gas flow rate and low initial PFOA concentration, the predictability of the concentration of dissolved ozone was improved (Fig. 8b,d,f), since the reduction of the surface tension, caused by the adsorption of PFOA molecules (surfactant) on the gas/water interfaces was weaker, and the foaming was not so intense. The PFOA removal efficiency has the tendency to increase from ~ 43 % to ~ 48 % as the ozone concentration increases (Fig. 8a,c,e). The concentration of ozone decomposition products C_R is very low at early and intermediate times, and reaches remarkable values at late times (Fig. S3a-c), with the PFOA degradation rate decreasing with time (Fig. 8a,c,e). In this manner, the indirect oxidation sustains the PFOA degradation at long times.

In another series of experiments performed at low initial PFOA

Fig. 7. (a,c,e,g) Simulated vs measured transient response of PFOA removal efficiency, and simulated ratio of direct PFOA oxidation rate to total PFOA oxidation rate. (b,d,f,h) Simulated vs measured transient response of dissolved ozone concentration. Time-averaged solution pH and temperature: (a,b) pH= 5.7, T = 27.8 °C; (c,d) pH= 5.2, T = 27.8 °C; (e,f) pH= 5.1, T = 27.7 °C; (g,h) pH= 4.9, T = 26.4 °C.

Fig. 8. (a,c,e) Simulated vs measured transient response of PFOA removal efficiency, and simulated ratio of direct PFOA oxidation rate to total PFOA oxidation rate. (b,d,f) Simulated vs measured transient response of dissolved ozone concentration. Time-averaged solution pH and temperature: (a,b) pH= 7.7, T = 21.6 °C; (c,d) pH= 5.4, T = 23.8 °C; (e,f) pH= 6.3, T = 22.4 °C.

concentration, and low gas flow rate, after six hours of treatment, the PFOA removal efficiency was quite high for low and high ozone concentrations ($\sim 78\%$, $C_{O_3,in}^g=6.0\text{ g/Nm}^3$; $\sim 74\%$, $C_{O_3,in}^g=11.0\text{ g/Nm}^3$; $\sim 70\%$, $C_{O_3,in}^g=45\text{ g/Nm}^3$; Fig. 9a,c,g), and low for a moderate ozone concentration ($\sim 34\%$, $C_{O_3,in}^g=6.0\text{ g/Nm}^3$; Fig. 9e) The lower flow rate (compared to the previous case, Fig. 8) implies a longer residence time for gas bubbles, facilitating the ozone dissolution and dispersion in liquid phase, and increasing the frequency of PFOA collisions with dissolved ozone or radicals of its decomposition, leading to higher PFOA degradation rate (Fig. 9a,c,g). For the three cases of high PFOA removal efficiency (Fig. 9a,c,g), the concentration of ozone decomposition products C_R becomes remarkable at late times (Fig. S4a,b,d), as the direct PFOA oxidation tends to cease, and indirect oxidation becomes

the dominant mechanism. The relatively low PFOA degradation rate observed during the longest period of ozonation in one case ($C_{O_3,in}^g=21\text{ g/Nm}^3$, Fig. 9e) indicates the slow direct and indirect oxidation of PFOA, in spite of the presence of high concentration ozone decomposition products for a long period (Fig. S4c). However, when this test was continued for another 6 h, an almost doubling of the PFOA removal efficiency was attained, which means that ozonation delayed due to unforeseeable factors (Fig. 9e). It's worth mentioning that for the three tests of this series (Fig. 9a,c,e), the PFOA concentrations were measured with UHPLC-HRMS method, while the initial and final concentrations of solutions were also measured by MBAS method (Table 4). The deviation of MBAS from LC-MS/MS ranges between 1.6 % and 10.8 % for the initial values, and between 11.1 % and 17.6 % for the

Fig. 9. (a,c,e,g) Simulated vs measured transient response of PFOA removal efficiency, and simulated ratio of direct PFOA oxidation rate to total PFOA oxidation rate. (b,d,f,h) Simulated vs measured transient response of dissolved ozone concentration. Time-averaged solution pH and temperature: (a,b) pH= 5.9, T = 21.4 °C; (c,d) pH= 5.7, T = 20.4 °C; (e,f) pH= 5.2, T = 19.1 °C; (g,h) pH= 4.2, T = 20.9 °C.

Table 4
Comparison of MBAS vs UHPLC-HRMS measurements.

$C_{O_3}^g$	Time t (h)	MBAS	UHPLC-HRMS	% deviation	Time t (h)	MBAS	UHPLC-HRMS	% deviation
6.0	0.0	11.9	12.1	1.6	6.0	2.4	2.7	11.1
11.0	0.0	8.5	8.1	4.7	6.0	2.4	2.1	12.5
21.0	0.0	10.2	9.1	10.8	12.0	3.4	2.8	17.6

Fig. 10. Comparison of the transient responses of the PFOA removal efficiency when the residual PFOA concentration is measured by MBAS and UHPLC-HRMS methods.

final values (Table 4) which are acceptable by accounting for the factors affecting the uncertainty of measurements (Fig. 6).

A comparative analysis of the two methods used to detect the PFOA concentration as a function of time is shown in Fig. 10, which depicts the PFOA removal efficiency for two ozonation experiments conducted at comparable conditions. The observed difference between the two responses is almost constant over the treatment time (~10 %, Fig. 10), and reasonable under the light of the multiple parameters affecting the evolution of ozonation (Fig. 6).

The measured values of the final concentration of fluoride, C_F (mg/L) along with the degree of defluorination, d_f (%) are shown in Table 5. Though the accuracy of fluoride (F^-) measurements by the fluorine sensor is questionable, particularly for high initial PFOA concentrations, the data suggest that the degree of defluorination of PFOA is an increasing function of injected ozone concentration (Table 5). The excess of dissolved ozone molecules stimulates the generation of active radicals more frequently and favors the subsequent decomposition of intermediate PFOA degradation products with the release of free fluoride anions.

The estimated parameter values along with the HPD intervals (error bars) are depicted in Fig. 11. The kinetic constant of the direct PFOA degradation, k_{PD} , ranges from 10^{-7} to 10^{-4} with the highest values occurring for low ozone concentration and low initial PFOA concentration (Fig. 11a). The steady-state PFOA concentration, $C_{P,eq}$, is proportional to the initial PFOA concentration and almost independent on

Table 5
Free fluorine anions concentration (mg/L) and degree of defluorination (%) at the end of ozonation tests.

Q (L/min)	C_{P0} (g/m ³)	$C_{O_3}^g \approx 5$ g/m ³	$C_{O_3}^g \approx 10$ g/m ³	$C_{O_3}^g \approx 20$ g/m ³	$C_{O_3}^g \approx 50$ g/m ³
0.1 g/m ³	≈50.0	1.7 (16.6)	2.5 (18.8)	4.3 (33.8)	8.1 (41.2)
0.2	≈10.0	0.9 (29.3)	1.2 (35.3)	1.8 (53.3)	-
0.1	≈10.0	1.3 (20.0)	1.6 (38.7)	1.9 (43.8)	-

the injected ozone concentration (Fig. 11b). The ozone mass consumed per PFOA direct degradation rate, α_D , takes non-zero values only for high gas flow rates and short retention times, while its zero values for PFOA degradation indicate very low (and probably not “quantifiable”) ozone consumption in relation to the ozone that decays (Fig. 11c). The ratio of actual ozone decomposition rate to the theoretical one, f , is a decreasing function of injected ozone concentration, due mainly to the limited concentration of dissolved ozone (Fig. 11d). The rate constant of indirect PFOA degradation, k_{PI} , ranges from 10^{-7} to 10^3 with the highest values occurring for high initial PFOA concentration (Fig. 11e), indicating that the excess of PFOA in aqueous solution triggers its oxidation by the ozone decomposition by-products, the concentration of which becomes quite high at long times (Figs. S2-S4). In one case, the very low values of both kinetic constants (Fig. 11a,e) are reflected in the slow PFOA degradation (Fig. 9e). The pseudo-component (O_3 decomposition products) mass consumed per PFOA indirect degradation rate, α_I , takes less and larger than unity values and seems to be independent of the ozone concentration in injected gas (Fig. 11f).

The consumption of energy per unit mass of degraded PFOA is shown in Fig. 12a-c. After 6 h of treatment, the energy expenditure for high initial PFOA concentration (~0.075–0.085 kWh/mg) is much less (Fig. 12a) than that (0.15–0.50 kWh/mg) for low initial PFOA concentration (Fig. 12b,c). The energy expenditure is almost independent of ozone concentration for high initial PFOA concentration (Fig. 12a) and may increase or decrease with the ozone concentration, depending on the ozone reactivity for low initial PFOA concentrations (Fig. 12b,c).

3.3. Formation of Short-Chain PFAS and Non-Target Analysis

Short-chain PFAS congeners generated during PFOA degradation were detected and quantified using UHPLC-HRMS via both targeted and non-targeted analysis. Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA) was the most prevalent, followed by perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA) and perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA), which were detected in all treated samples but were absent in the reference samples (untreated). Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA), although included in the target method, was not detected. The concentrations of even PFHpA (10–30 μ g/L in photocatalysis and 3–10 μ g/L in ozonation) were much less than the residual PFOA concentrations observed at the end of the tests (1.9 mg/L in photocatalysis and 2.4 mg/L in ozonation). The low PFOA degradation rate during photocatalysis is reflected in the gradual increase of the concentration of all short-chain substances at early times, and their stabilization at late times (Fig. 13a) when the PFOA concentration does not decrease any more (Fig. 5b). As the concentration of injected ozone doubles, the concentration of short-chain substances decreases by one order of magnitude (Fig. 13b-d), and such changes are consistent with the observed decrease of PFOA degradation rate and removal efficiency (Fig. 9a,c,e).

Non-target analysis was conducted to further investigate potential degradation products, at the end of the three ozonation tests (Fig. 9a,c,e). This analysis revealed the presence of 13 PFAS congeners, identified with varying degrees of confidence (Supporting Information; Table S3). Among these, perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids (PFCAs), including PFHpA, PFHxA, and PFPeA, were identified with the highest certainty, and residual PFOA remained the most abundant peak in the ozonation tests.

In addition, perfluoro-n-ethanoic acid (i.e., Trifluoroacetic acid, TFA) was identified as the second most abundant peak, with a relative

Fig. 11. Parameter values estimated by fitting the numerical predictions of the TSM model to the experimentally measured transient responses of PFOA and dissolved ozone concentrations. (a) Direct PFOA degradation rate constant, k_{PD} . (b) Steady-state PFOA concentration, $C_{P,eq}$. (c) Ozone consumed per PFOA direct degradation rate, α_D . (d) Ratio of actual ozone decomposition rate to the theoretical one, f . (e) Indirect PFOA degradation rate constant, k_{PI} . (f) Ozone consumed per PFOA indirect degradation rate, α_I .

peak area similar in terms of order of magnitude with that of the residual PFOA (Table S3; Supporting Information). Partially fluorinated intermediates, including 2H-Perfluorooctanoic acid (a variant of PFOA) and 3H-Perfluorobutanoic acid (a variant of PFBA), were also detected. However, both were present only in trace amounts compared to TFA (Table S3). The foregoing findings suggest that TFA is the main by-product of the degradation of PFOA by ozonation. TFA is a strong acid having an ionization constant about 34,000 higher than that of acetic

acid, it is harmful when inhaled, causes severe skin burns and is toxic for aquatic organisms even at low concentrations.

3.4. Comparative analysis of ozonation and photocatalysis

The comparative presentation of the performance of photo-degradation and ozonation processes is summarized in Table 6. In photocatalysis with immobilized ZnO nanoparticles, the PFOA removal

Fig. 12. Energy consumed per unit mass of PFOA degraded during ozonation tests in bubble flow reactor. (a) $Q_G = 0.1$ L/min, $C_{P0} = 50$ mg/L; (b) $Q_G = 0.2$ L/min, $C_{P0} = 10$ mg/L; (c) $Q_G = 0.1$ L/min, $C_{P0} = 10$ mg/L.

efficiency vary from 22 % to 92 % with the energy consumption ranging between 0.1 and 0.35 kWh/mg-PFOA (Table 6). The UV-photo-oxidation of PFOA with and without catalyst is a slow process (3–6 days, Fig. 5) but it has the tendency to remain active even at very long times, and after many cycles of reuse (Fig. 5a,b) outlining the durability of photocatalysts. The optimal PFOA degradation conditions (Table 6) occur for ZnO-DN ($R_E = 93$ %, $E_m = 0.186$ kWh/mg) and ZnO-DN-Ag ($R_E = 70.5$ %, $E_m = 0.109$ kWh/mg) confirming the long period of photocatalytic activation for immobilized ZnO.

Depending on the initial PFOA concentration, the gas flow rate, and initial concentration of injected ozone, the PFOA removal efficiency by ozonation may range from 32 % to 78 % with the maximum values (70–78 %) achieved at low PFOA concentrations and low flow rates (Table 6). According to the interpretation of results from numerical simulations, the direct ozone oxidation is dominant mechanism over early and intermediate times, while the indirect oxidation by ozone decomposition products becomes evident over late times (Figs. 7–9; Figs. S2–S4). For relatively long gas retention times ($Q_g = 0.1$ L/min) the optimal conditions for degradation at high ($C_{P0} \sim 50$ mg/L) and low ($C_{P0} \sim 10$ mg/L) initial PFOA concentration occur at high ($C_{O_3,in}^g = 45$ g/m³, $R_E = 57$ %, $E_m = 0.080$ kWh/mg), and low ($C_{O_3,in}^g = 6$ g/m³, $R_E = 78$ %, $E_m = 0.15$ kWh/mg) ozone concentration, respectively (Table 6). For relatively short gas retention times ($Q_g = 0.2$ L/min) the dependence of R_E and E_m on ozone concentration has the tendency to weaken (Table 6). Evidently, ozonation is less efficient than photocatalysis (maximum $R_E \sim 78$ vs 93 %), although the energy expenditure is comparable for the two processes (0.155 vs 0.186 kWh/mg).

In earlier studies, photocatalysis and photolysis appeared more efficient than ozonation for the decomposition of PFOA (Huang et al., 2016). However, the power of UVC-lamp was quite high (4X28W) and suspended nanoparticles of photocatalyst (TiO_2) were used, in contrast to the present study where lamps of lower power (1X6W) and photocatalysts immobilized on non-porous substrates (ZnO, Fe-doped ZnO) were used. On the other hand, the ozonation of fluorotelomer unsaturated carboxylic acids (FTUCA) was more efficient than photolysis with the main products of degradation being PFCAs (Anumol et al., 2016). In addition, earlier studies have revealed that PFOA can be substantially degraded by ozonation at alkaline conditions (pH \sim 11), while the pre-treatment of solution with ozonation at ambient pH (\sim 5) for a short period facilitates the ozone dissolution so that the hydroxyl and other radicals generated at high pH trigger chain reactions leading to the extensive degradation of PFOA (Lin et al., 2012).

The photocatalytic degradation of PFOA depends strongly on the catalyst type, and previous usage time in photo-oxidation reactions (aging). Evidently, the process performance might be improved respectably by utilizing other photocatalysts, and higher power UV-radiation (Qanbarzadeh et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2021). However, in photocatalysis, there is no need for the addition of chemicals in treated solution, whereas the process could become more cost-effective if the treatment time was shortened, since neither the UV-lamp nor the recirculation pump are energy-intensive devices. On the other hand, the performance of ozonation might be improved if several factors, favoring the ozone decomposition to active intermediate species, were adjusted with the addition of chemicals: for instance, the pH could be controlled over the alkaline range (9–11), while with the

Fig. 13. Transient responses of PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA during (a) photocatalysis (Fig. 5b) and (b,c,d) ozonation tests (Fig. 9a-f).

Table 6

PFOA removal efficiency and energy expenditure for photocatalysis and ozonation.

Photocatalysis and photolysis tests (duration=90 h)					
Catalyst	C_{p0} (mg/L)	V_R+V_T (L)	PFOA Removal Efficiency, R_E	Energy expenditure, E_m (kWh/mg)	
ZnO-DN	25.1	250	0.926	0.1858	
Fe-ZnO-SL	25.7	250	0.610	0.1993	
PHL-1	14.4	550	0.249	0.123	
PHL-2	5.1	550	0.364	0.2155	
Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag	9.6	450	0.218	0.3555	
Fe-ZnO-SL-Ag-Air	17.2	450	0.363	0.1622	
ZnO-DN-Ag	33.3	450	0.705	0.1089	
Ozonation tests					
C_{p0} (mg/L)	$C_{O_3,in}^g$ (g/m ³)	Q_g (L/min)	PFOA Removal Efficiency, R_E	Energy Efficiency, E_m (kWh/mg)	Duration (h)
46.9	6.0	0.1	0.316	0.0857	6
43.6	10.9	0.1	0.443	0.0756	6
51.6	21.8	0.1	0.358	0.0829	6
50.1	45.5	0.1	0.569	0.0809	6
12.1	6.0	0.1	0.777	0.1547	6
8.1	11.0	0.1	0.741	0.2607	6
9.1	21.0	0.1	0.341	0.4894	6
9.1	21.0	0.1	0.692	0.516	12
10.3	45.0	0.1	0.699	0.3287	6
10.4	6.9	0.2	0.427	0.3013	6
10.4	11.3	0.2	0.475	0.2996	6
10.2	21.8	0.2	0.481	0.2352	6

addition of hydrogen peroxide the efficiency of oxidation reactions could be improved substantially (Lin et al., 2012). Moreover, ozonation coupled with adsorption and membrane filtration might become very effective (Thompson et al., 2011; Flores et al., 2013; Huang et al., 2016).

3.5. Summary of the most important results

In summary, the novelties of the present work are highlighted as follows: lab-scale recirculation and semi-batch tests were combined with true-to-the-physics numerical models to decouple the mass-transfer from reactive processes and elucidate the effects of experimental conditions on the kinetics of PFOA degradation when applying photocatalysis and ozonation to relatively high (~10–50 mg/L) concentration solutions at ambient pH (5–7.5). The deviation of the PFOA concentrations measured with the cost-effective and fast MBAS method from those measured with the expensive, time-consuming, and high throughput UHPLC-HRMS method were acceptable. Numerical modeling revealed that ozonation was dominated by the direct ozone oxidation over early times, and indirect oxidation by generated active species over late times. Very low concentrations of short-chain congeners (C5–C7) were detected for photocatalysis and ozonation, and TFA was identified as the dominant residual byproduct of ozonation. For photocatalysis, the highest PFOA removal efficiency with relatively low energy expenditure was achieved by using either virgin ($R_E \sim 93\%$, $E_m \sim 0.19$ kWh/mg-PFOA) or aged ($R_E \sim 70\%$, $E_m \sim 0.11$ kWh/mg-PFOA) ZnO nanoparticles immobilized on Duranit beads. For ozonation, the highest PFOA removal efficiencies were achieved at low (~10 mg/L) initial PFOA concentration and low gas flow rates ($R_E \sim 70$ –77%), while the energy expenditure was

minimized ($E_m \sim 0.075\text{--}0.085$ kWh/mg-PFOA) for high initial (~ 50 mg/L) PFOA concentrations.

Based on the abovementioned characteristics of PFOA photocatalysis and ozonation, their combination could enable the reduction of both the treatment time and energy expenditure. Indeed, in earlier studies, the titania-based photocatalytic ozonation of PFOA has been proven a high performance degradation method, with the defluorination ratio reaching $\sim 44\%$, thanks to the combined action of photogenerated holes and hydroxyl radicals (Huang et al., 2016).

4. Conclusions

In an attempt to assess the PFAS degradability by advanced oxidation processes, aqueous solutions of PFOA with concentrations in the range 10–50 mg/L were tested with two setups: (i) a photoreactor equipped with a UV-C lamp, packed with beads coated by ZnO-based photocatalysts, and connected with a tank for the continuous recirculation of PFOA solution; (ii) a semi-batch bubble flow reactor filled with the PFOA solution and equipped with a mass-flow controller capable to inject the ozone rich gas through a porous diffuser. PFOA photodegradation experiments were conducted with: Fe-doped ZnO photocatalyst, undoped ZnO photocatalyst, UV-irradiation and no catalyst (photolysis), Fe-doped ZnO catalyst and no UV-radiation (sorption). In addition, PFOA ozonation experiments were done by varying the gas flow rate (0.1, 0.2 L/min), the ozone concentration ($5\text{--}50$ g/m³) and the initial PFOA concentration (10, 50 mg/L) so that the ozone dosage ranges from 35 mg/h to 270 mg/h. In general, the PFOA concentration as a function of time was measured by the MBAS extraction method in combination with the UV-Vis spectroscopy. In order to evaluate the reliability of the method for reactive systems, and detect the potential generation of intermediate short-chain substances in a series of photocatalysis and ozonation tests, the PFOA concentration was measured by the UHPLC-HRMS method. The PFOA photodegradation was modeled by an advection-dispersion-reaction model, while the PFOA ozonation was approximated by the two-phase TSM model. Both models were utilized to estimate the unknown kinetic parameters of PFOA degradation with inverse modeling of experimental results. The consumption of energy per unit mass of degraded PFOA was calculated as a function of time for all experiments, and used as a measure to assess the energy expenditure for each process. The most important conclusions are outlined below.

- The photocatalytic degradation of PFOA is a time-consuming process with its kinetics depending on the type and time of previous usage (ageing) of immobilized photocatalysts, the PFOA removal efficiency reaching 70–90 %, and the energy efficiency ranging from 0.1 to 0.2 kWh/mg, when using ZnO-coated Duranit beads.
- Application of ozonation over ambient pH values (5–7.5), leads to PFOA removal efficiencies from 30 % to 78 %, depending on the gas flow rate, the initial PFOA concentration, and the concentration of injected ozone; the highest PFOA removal efficiencies ($\sim 70\text{--}78\%$) are obtained when both the flow rate of injected gas and the initial PFOA concentration are low; the energy expenditure is minimized for high values of the initial PFOA concentration.
- According to the TSM model, the ozonation rate is dominated by the direct ozone oxidation over early and intermediate times, and indirect oxidation by ozone decomposition products over late times.
- MBAS-UV-vis and UHPLC-HRMS provide comparable results, with the deviation between measured concentrations to increase with the treatment time.
- The degree of PFOA defluorination is high for photolysis, very low for photocatalysis, and increase with the injected ozone concentration increasing.
- Short-chain perfluorocarboxylic acids (C7-C5) were detected with high confidence as intermediate products of PFOA degradation from both degradation approaches (photocatalysis and ozonation) at

concentrations approximately 2 orders of magnitude lower than those of the residual PFOA levels. Non-target analysis identified trifluoroacetic acid as the main byproduct of PFOA degradation during ozonation.

4.1. Perspectives for future work

Among the two methods, it seems that: (i) photocatalysis on immobilized ZnO-based photocatalysts is a slow process, and cost-effective in terms of energy consumption; (ii) ozonation is a fast and energy-intensive process, with its performance being regulated with the adjustment of process parameters (e.g. flow rate, ozone concentration). Presumably, photocatalysis might become more efficient, in terms of treatment time, if combined with ozonation: for instance, an ozone rich gas could be injected in the photoreactor for enhancing PFOA oxidation (Huang et al., 2016; Lashuk et al., 2022). Moreover, two disadvantages of both advanced oxidation processes, used as standalone methods for the remediation of aqueous solutions containing PFAS at high concentration, are the relatively low degree of defluorination, and the generation of a mixture of short-chained byproducts that might be equally or more toxic than the parent substances (e.g. TFA). So, emphasis should be placed on the development of methods for the elimination of the residual PFAS and complete defluorination. A potential solution might be the treatment of PFAS-contaminated water with appropriately-designed hybrid AOPs so that the synergistic performance of the processes (e.g. photocatalytic ozonation) is optimized. However, even then, some traces of parent or daughter components will remain in the aqueous solution, so that additional treatment will be necessary. A possible solution would be the post-treatment with functional adsorbent materials capable of removing all remaining contaminants (Ganesh Kumar et al., 2023). Cascade systems of hybrid AOPs connected with functional adsorbents might be regarded as a future plan for the elimination of PFAS from water matrices.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Davide Rotondo: Validation, Formal analysis. **Masho Hilawie Belay:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Maria Theodoropoulou:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Nadia Bali:** Validation, Software. **Francesco Dondero:** Validation, Resources, Project administration. **Emilio Marengo:** Formal analysis. **Elisa Robotti:** Validation, Data curation. **Michalis Karavasilis:** Visualization, Methodology. **Konstantinos Christodoulis:** Visualization, Investigation. **Anastasios Melitsiotis:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tsakiroglou Christos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.psep.2025.107477](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2025.107477).

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